

MUSEUM PENDIDIKAN INDONESIA: HAS IT BEEN USEFUL?

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ABSTRACT

This paper is a case study of Museum Pendidikan Indonesia where the Head of Museum and some visitors of this Museum had been interviewed. Related to the selection of case study model, the writer wanted to raise the thing to the surface until it becomes public knowledge. Furthermore, this case study is a Retrospective Case Study, which allows for the follow-up of treatment or improvement of a case. The objective was to find out whether the Museum has used optimally as a learning resource. Therefore, interview methods has been chosen to strengthen and clarify the data obtained is about utilization and management of the Museum. To sum up the interview result, the Museums has been maximal in completing its role. The result showed that Museum Pendidikan Indonesia had been used as a learning resource. However, this museum still needs to do quality improvement regarding collection, display, promotion, and system.

KEYWORDS

Retrospective Case Study, Museum Pendidikan Indonesia, Learning resource

1. INTRODUCTION

Each student has different learning problems since they have different characteristic and learning style. As Barringer, Pohlman, and Robinson stated that students have individual characteristics that facilitate the degree of success they have with particular intervention programs [1]. This causes a difference in determining the strategy and ways of learning of students, because of different ways of learning then different strategies and media will be applied [2]. Therefore, the students need various resources to figure it out. One of which is learning through a museum. Museum's role is to present its collections to the public to foster the development of science, education and pleasure [3]. In addition, according to Caleb Setiawan (Devi, 1996; 7) museum is a building to place a collection of objects to be investigated, studied and enjoyed [4]. The museum collects materials from different places and different times into a building. Not only that, but the museum also becomes a permanent institution to maintain, investigate, teach, exhibit and demonstrate objects of conservation to the public for publication, information, education, and recreation.

Moreover, the most recent definition based on 21st International Congress of Museum (ICOM) 2007 in Vienna, Austria, defines museum as a fixed non-profit institution serving the community and its development, open to the public, collecting, caring, researching, communicating, and exhibiting human relics and its environment, both tangible and intangible for learning, education, and entertainment [5]. In the light of this, there was a positive strong argument from Head of Museum who said this Museum has been functioned as a learning resources. Therefore, the aim of this paper is to know how far Museum Pendidikan Indonesia of Yogyakarta State University as one of the learning resources is useful for academic society.

The writer will conduct this study into a study case research about how the society utilized Museum Pendidikan Indonesia in Yogyakarta State University as one of the learning resources.

According to Bogdan and Biklen (1982) case studies are a detailed test of a single background or a subject person or document storage or one particular event [6]. Surakhmad (1982) limited the case study as an approach by focusing on an intensive and detailed case [7]. While Ary, Jacobs, and Razavieh (1985) provide that in case studies the researcher should attempt to test the unit or individual in detail [8]. Yin (1987) made it clear that more technical limitations with an emphasis on its characteristics [9].

According to Endraswara (2003: 78), case studies can be divided into two groups, namely case studies in the form of deviations from fairness and case studies to a positive development [10]. This study will be in a case study to positive development. Equally important, case studies are also conducted in a natural, holistic and profound setting. Natural means data acquisition activities are conducted in real-life events. There is no need for certain treatments either on the subject or the context in which the research is conducted. Then holistic, it means researchers should be able to obtain information that will be comprehensive data so as not to leave the remaining information. The data will be obtained fact or reality. With this intention, Yunus (2010: 264) describes the object studied in the Case Study only imaging himself in depth/detail / complete to obtain the whole picture of the object (wholeness) in the sense that the data collected in the study is studied as a whole [11]. Thereunto, this study is a Restropective Case Study, which allows for the follow-up of treatment or improvement of a case [10]. Hence, the writer come up with the idea of Museum Pendidikan Indonesia; Has it been useful? The research question will be How is the use of Museum Pendidikan Indonesia as a learning resource?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. LEARNING RESOURCES

According to Brown et al. (1996) in Chen (2016), learning resources are sets of information stored in various media and forms that aim to assist students in understanding the lesson [12]. When students meet problems in their learning proses, they need resources to encounter their problem, as Chiu (2010) stated that students would search or ask for learning resources to help them solve their problem. Furthermore, Brown et al. (1996) also state that learning resources were used to help students' learning and to solve their learning problems [12]. In the area of instructional technology also give some explanation about definitions of learning resources. The definition and area of AECT 1977 define instructional technology as a complex and integrated process involving people, procedures, ideas, tools, and organizations to analyze problems, find ways to solve, implement, evaluate, and manage problem-solving that concerns all aspects of human learning [13]. In this definition, emphasize on all educational problems by using learning resources. Learning resources in question is a source of learning related both by design and by utilization. Meanwhile, according to AECT 1994 educational technology translated into a narrower learning technology [14]. This definition is the theory and practice of the design, development, utilization, management, and evaluation of processes and resources for learning. The formulation of AECT 1994 further refers to the use of theories in the practice of applying learning technology in schools. The definition of instructional technology continues to grow to AECT 2004. AECT 2004 defines it as a study and ethical practice to facilitate learning and improve performance through the creation, use, and management of technology processes and resources [15]. Based on the description of AECT 1977, 1994, and 2004 there are some differences, it is summarized as follows:

1. AECT 1977 defines learning resources as all sources (data, people, and goods) that can be used by learners as a separate source or in combination to facilitate learning [13]. Also, AECT 1977 translates that every educational and instructional problem can be solved by learning resources. In this case, the learning resources in AECT 1977 are messages, people, materials, tools, techniques, and background (environment).

2. AECT 1994, learning resources are not the only solution to learning problems, but learning resources are also used to facilitate learners' learning [14]. Problem-solving of learning by using the various ways both theoretically and practically from the five areas of the area that include design, development, utilization, management, and assessment.
3. While, AECT 2004 specifies learning resources ranging from the simplest media, including the presentation of materials from teachers to the use of technology, information and communication (ICT) for the learning process (compared: Prawiradilaga, 2007) [16]. Learning process is not only done through face-to-face meetings but also through online learning or telelearning because someone wants to learn and facilitated well so that the learning process occurs. Also, this definition affirms the role of instructional technology in the organization to improve performance. The concept of organizational development for instructional technology makes the concept of performance technology useful for various organizational characteristics.

This indicates that the definition of the source of learning increasingly looks towards its usefulness, not just as problem-solving (AECT 1977) or as a learning facility (AECT 1994), but also can improve the learner's performance. Thus, the role of learning resources in assisting students' learning is very important, of course by knowing what characteristic of learning resources is.

2.2. CHARACTERISTIC OF LEARNING RESOURCES

Broadly, the source of learning has the following characteristics:

1. Learning resources should be able to provide strength in teaching and learning process so that instructional goals can be achieved optimally.
2. Learning resources must have instructional values that can change and bring perfect changes to the behavior of existing goals.

By the classification of learning resources, the learning resources that are utilized have the following characteristics: a) Unorganized and systematic in both form and content. b) Only used according to circumstances and certain purposes. Learning resources designed (resource by signed) (Rohani, 1997) [17].

2.3. MUSEUM AS LEARNING RESOURCES

A museum, as defined by the International Council of Museums (ICOM 2007), is "a permanent institution in the service of society and its development, and open to the public, obtaining, preserving, researching, communicating and exhibiting, for study, education and pleasure purposes [18]. "The museum has a natural role as an educational institution. Ambrose and Paine (1994) argue that the museum's education mission is to improve the education of children and adults through the imaginative use of museums and collections and to help museums maximize the educational potential of collections, buildings and other information sources"(p45) [19]. Hence, the museum has a mission of providing the study, education, and enjoyment for the general public (ICOM, 2007) [18]. This is a reference that the museum beside being a choice of tourist destinations as it functions, such as local tours, the museum should also be an interesting place to educate people about the culture and history of a nation.

2.4. TYPES OF MUSEUM

As can be seen from the name and vision and mission of the Museum Pendidikan Indonesia in Yogyakarta State University, this museum is categorized as science and technology museum. Furthermore, this museum serves as a learning resource where it needs to foster the spirit of

nationalism through the world of education, creating an educational laboratory as a learning and research place for the academic community and society, and to grow and develop the spirit and commitment of academic community and society to always be creative in improving the quality of education.

As mentioned in the book of *The Museum; Its History and Its Tasks in Education* that museum is a place to store any goods and the place to exhibit anything, where in this book described museum could become a place to learn and to entertain through all things that museum store and exhibit [20]. It is in line with Government Regulation No. 66 of 2015 on the museum, shown in chapter two that the museum has duties for assessment, education, and pleasure [21].

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. DESIGN OF THE STUDY

This research is a case study which looks at the function of the Museum of Education of Indonesia in Yogyakarta State University as one of the learning resources that utilized maximally. The Case Study is a series of intensive, detailed and profound scientific activities about a program, event, and activity, whether on an individual level, a group of people, institutions, or organizations to gain in-depth knowledge of the event. Typically, the selected event from now on referred to as the case is the real-life event, which is in progress, not something that has passed. Yin (1994: 21) a Case Study should not only ask about "what", but also "how" and "why". The "what" question is meant to gain descriptive knowledge, how to acquire explanative knowledge, and "why" is to acquire explorative knowledge [9]. The reasons why the writer took case study as the model of it because by using this method the thing will be raised to the surface until it became public knowledge. Furthermore, this case study is a Retrospective Case Study, which allows for the follow-up of treatment or improvement of a case.

3.2. SUBJECT OF STUDY

Determination of research samples will be done by using Purposive Sampling where sampling is based on the purpose of this case study. Purposive sampling is a sampling method by choosing a subject based on specific criteria what this study needs. Therefore the subjects of this study were both organizers and visitors of the museum.

3.3. TECHNIQUE OF DATA COLLECTION

According to Arikunto (2009), the way to collect data used in program evaluation is the same as the method used in research, the type of method is a questionnaire, interview, observation, test, documentation and inventory [22]. This study used interviews to collect data. According to Sugiyono (2010: 194), understanding the interview as follows:

“Interview is used as data collection techniques if the researcher will conduct a preliminary study to find the problems to be researched, and also the researcher wants to know the things from the more in-depth respondents and the number of respondents slightly / small” [23].

In collecting the data, the writer proposed some structured questions to fulfil what this study needs. The interview process was given to the students who visit the museum and to the museum employees. The purpose of using interview methods is to strengthen and clarify the data obtained that is about the utilization and management of the Museum Pendidikan Indonesia. Hence, the instrument used in this study was interview sheets.

Then, for the data analysis techniques used in this study include a transcript of interview result, data reduction, analysis, and data interpretation. From the results of data analysis can then be deduced.

The following is a data analysis technique used by researchers:

1. Data reduction; data reduction is defined as the selection process, focusing on simplification, abstraction, and transformation of coarse data arising from written records in the field. Data reduction activities are on-going, especially during data collection. There was a reduction stage, which is making a summary, coding, tracing the theme, creating clusters, creating partitions, and writing a memo.
2. Deciding a conclusion; as data collection is done, researchers began to look for the meaning of things, noting order, patterns, explanations, possible configurations, causal paths, and propositions. The conclusions emerged depending on the size of the collection of field notes, coding, storage, and retrieval methods used, the researcher's skills and the demands of the funder.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this case study, the writer took the data by interviewing the Head of Museum Pendidikan Indonesia and some visitors of Museum Pendidikan Indonesia. The first interview is done between writer and Head of Museum, as in Table 1.

Table 1. Interview Result with Head of Museum Pendidikan Indonesia

No.	Questions	Answer
1.	Is this museum can be regarded as a source of learning?	Yes, it is. This museum has so far been functioning as one source of learning. Therefore this museum can be said as one source of learning.
2.	What are the museum programs in fulfilling its role as a source of learning?	So far the activities of the museum to fulfil its role as one of the learning resources are as follows: 1. Discussion of nationalities, 2. English speaking; object material museum objects, 3. comic exhibitions; in it contains character education about heroism; visualizing historical stories, development from the past to the present; become a medium for character education, and 4. The little puppeteer festival as a form preservation and education of culture.
3.	What is the plan of this Museum to maximize its function as one of the learning resources?	Future concept: 1. The Museum team will be no longer a guide, but an educator, 2. This Museum will use triangulation model. It will connect three important parts of the university that are the source

		<p>of information, i.e., library, museum, and archiving section that makes it easy to search data,</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Fulfilment of data collection. 4. Digitalization system, 5. Exhibition every three months, and 6. Each month Museum will organize academic film screening that serves as a means to support students' creativity through cooperation with faculty at Yogyakarta State University, as it has been done, that is the film screening of German education and technology development by students of German Education, Faculty of Languages and Arts of YSU.
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Based on the interview result, the role of the Museum as a learning resource has been maximal. So far, the Museum Pendidikan Indonesia has held several activities to fulfil its role as a learning resource, including the discussion of nationality and English speaking club held by the students of the Faculty of Language and Arts of Yogyakarta State University. The objects in the Museum become the object of discussion. Also, the Museum Pendidikan Indonesia also holds a comic exhibition in which it contains character education on heroism; visualizing historical stories, development from the past to the present; as well as being a medium for character education. Besides that, for the future concept, the Museum will make an exhibition of YSU achievements. This exhibition aimed to motivate and stimulate visitors to grow through achievements that have been achieved; to achieve new achievements for the present generation to be more advanced and showcased the works of outstanding figures from Yogyakarta State University.

The Museum Head's opinion above is also reinforced by some visitor responses. The writer also interviewed with some visitors. Some of the are university students, and other were high school students. The data is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Interview Result with Vistors pof Museum Pendidikan Indonesia

No.	Questions	Student's Name	Answer
1.	What is your purpose in visiting this Museum?	Student 1	My purpose of visiting this Museum is to know more about this Museum.
		Student 2	My purpose of visiting this Museum is to know more about what is on display at this Museum
		Student 3	My purpose to visit this Museum is to find out why this museum is quiet and why YSU students are not flocking to come here. I want to answer this questions.

		Student 4	My goal came to this Museum are for recreation and seeking experience.
		Student 5	I came here because my lecture asks my class to do visitation.
2.	After walking around the Museum, what information do you get?	Student 1	I know then, the Museum is not only for History students. I found some general thing such as information on currency developments in Indonesia, which is important to know by the community.
		Student 2	I known that in the museum, the things are not only the stuff of pure historical science but also about the development of general education from time to time.
		Student 3	I got much information about the history of education in Indonesia.
		Student 4	I finally saw the real firsthand money.
		Student 5	I know about the education development.
3.	In your opinion, is this Museum Pendidikan Indonesia can be used as one of the learning resources?	Student 1	Yes, it can.
		Student 2	Yes, it can.
		Student 3	Yes, it can.
		Student 4	Yes, it can.
		Student 5	Yes, it can.
4.	Which are the most interesting spots of collections of Museum Pendidikan Indonesia?	Student 1	Regarding art and display, the interesting is the comic space.
		Student 2	regarding science, the displays space of Mathematics and Natural Sciences tools was very interesting for me, because it was quite informative, so it can add insight about the old tools which these tools are not found in many places except in particular museums, such in this Museum
		Student 3	I think the most interesting space was the old money collection room.
		Student 4	I think the most interesting side of this museum was the <i>onthel</i> bike showcase as it shows the educational side of the old days where people were driving by bicycle to school.
		Student 5	The most eye-catching room

			was comic room exhibition.
5.	What are your expectations for this Museum?	Student 1	Hopefully, in future, this Museum Pendidikan Indonesia can continue to add and complete the collections.
		Student 2	2. Information displayed on each collection should be added, as there are still many museum collections displayed but without description.
		Student 3	Hopefully, in the future, Museum Pendidikan Indonesia has many educators so that when the small group visit the museum can still be accompanied to explain dan give detail information about museum collections.
		Student 4	It is better if the layout of museum collections can be further grouped so the visitor can get clear information about one collection category.
		Student 5	Due to the lack of socialization about this museum which makes the students in UNY is not often visit this Museum, so hopefully, this museum can strengthen the promotion or dissemination of information about the activities held in this museum.

After conducting interviews with all respondents, the writer can conclude that the Indonesian Education Museum really can be used as a learning resource. According to them, this is evidenced by the layout and collections displayed in this Museum. For example, Comic Room, from art and displays point of view, this space is very interesting, studio layout with a variety of comics on display and the atmosphere is set as visitors enter the different dimensions eras make this room very interesting. Furthermore, regarding science, the laboratory display room is a room that makes visitors will be very excited because the tools on display are informative, this room also adds visitor insight into old laboratory tools, such as the microscope. These tools are not found in many places except certain museums, especially in this Museum. Moreover, the money collection room, according to them there is a feeling of excitement over the increasing knowledge of money development from ancient times until now.

Not only had those students who met by the author during the interview, but the author also met high school students who come from other universities and provinces. What they come to this museum is to add insight into the development of education in Indonesia. Sure enough, they get it after touring around the museum room. A student from SMA 1 Menggala, Bandar Lampung said, the most interesting side of the museum was in the *Onthel* bike showroom as it showed the educational side of the old days where people were driving by bicycle. He said that he can imagine how the former people went to school very different from now by reading the collection description. Furthermore, the role of Indonesian Education Museum as a source of learning is also

increasingly seen by making this Museum as a mandatory visitation program from outside parties, one of it is Santa Dharma University Yogyakarta. Based on the results of interviews with one of its students, the visitation program of Museum Pendidikan Indonesia is a mandatory program for new students, so it can be concluded that the whole museum has been useful for the community, especially students both from and outside the Yogyakarta State University.

However, from the opinions above, there are some things that need to be addressed such as the collection is still lacking because not all the corners and space in the museum is filled by the collection, so there are some angles and space. It would be very good if the museum continues to add and complete the collection. Another thing is the description of each collection on display, according to visitors the information displayed should be added, because there are still many museum collections are displayed without any description. Even if the description is not so detailed, it can be covered if when visitors go around the Museum accompanied by a guide or museum educator.

Correspondingly, the layout of museum collections, according to their collections, it will be better if the collections are grouped based on its category. Furthermore, the students of this university are rarely visited. As Pamadhi (2017) said, this museum is more visited by elementary, high school, and another university students or even students from different provinces. According to him, this happens because of the lack of socialization about this museum to the students, so later Museum can strengthen the promotion or dissemination of information about the activities held in this museum so they can visit this Museum more.

Coupled with the statements above, the Museum Pendidikan Indonesia will continue to enhance its role as a learning resource by using triangulation model, which will link the three important sections of the university that are the source of information, namely, libraries, museums, and archives. Triangulation form is intended to facilitate the search data (database system). Therefore, according to Head of Museum Pendidikan Indonesia, Hadjar Pamadhi said that it is necessary to fulfil the data collection, digitalization system, exhibition every three months, and there will be academic film screening every month; as a means to support students' creativity, realization to do cooperation with each Faculty of the State University of Yogyakarta. For instance, cooperation that has been implemented was the film screening handled by students of German Education about the development of education and technology of Germany.

5. CONCLUSIONS

As has been noted, the Museum Pendidikan Indonesia has used as a learning resource. The statements of Head of Museum and some visitors' opinion become the supporting of it. They said that all the activities that have been implemented in this museum to fulfil its role as a learning resource and the collections that have been displayed, people can learn and get some information. Similarly, those activities aimed to add insight and knowledge about the development of national education as written in its vision and mission, those are to carry out its function as a source of information about the development of national education, as a source of science and learning technology in order to educate the nation's life, and become a cultural and educational recreation facility. Therefore, has Museum Pendidikan Indonesia been useful as learning resources? Yes, it has.

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